

DIGITAL LEARNING TOOLS IN TEACHING MEDICAL TERMS IN ENGLISH

Guzacheva Nadiya Islamovna

senior teacher

Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12633230>

Modern education has become an arena of intense changes due to the rapid development of information technology. In the era of the digital revolution, the emphasis is shifting from traditional educational methods to innovative approaches, where digital technologies are becoming a key element of the educational process. This transformation not only reflects changes in society, where information has become the main resource, but also creates new requirements for the education system. Now we live in a world where technology is omnipresent, where education knows it has community support, recognizes its value, and recognizes that it increasingly depends on how well education harnesses the transformative potential of digital technology. Due to the ubiquitous presence of technology, teaching methods have also undergone certain changes.

In order to determine the priority directions for systemic reform of higher education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, raising the process of training independently thinking highly qualified personnel with modern knowledge and high spiritual and moral qualities to a qualitatively new level, modernizing higher education, developing the social sphere and economic sectors based on advanced educational technologies, it was Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev dated October 8, 2019 No. UP-5847 “On approval of the Concept for the development of the higher education system until 2030” was signed [1].

Practical skills in the implementation of digital educational technologies are of great importance in the process of digital education. With the introduction of online education, indirect connections are observed, which means that the range of

interaction is constantly increasing. Thus, online interaction is a system of relations that represents innovative models of educational content, economics of education, management of the digital education system and educational policy, development and testing for the professional community and society as a whole.

The most common language of international communication in the medical community is English. More than 90% of publications on medicine and healthcare are published in this language. The world's leading information technologies, digital devices, and elementary programming languages also use English. It is obvious that confident command of a foreign language for professional purposes is one of the priorities of quality medical education.

In the last few years, we have seen the active development of new forms of organizing student education at universities. The conditions of the pandemic, which led to the need to conduct classes remotely, outlined a new vector of development in matters of teaching in higher education. Digital technologies are updated so quickly that not every teacher can keep up with the skills to work with these technologies. However, universities in general are struggling for their image, including in terms of attracting and retaining the interest of potential students. Traditional forms of classes, regardless of whether it is a lecture or a practical lesson, should be interesting and interactive, but at the same time, they should not lose quality. In this sense, the teacher is now in quite strict conditions: educator has to worry about both the quality of the content of the lesson and the form of its presentation to students using modern technologies. At the same time, it is necessary to be prepared to move classes online.

A modern university graduate must have the following digital competencies:

- communication and cooperation in the digital environment;
- self-development;
- creative thinking;
- information and data management;
- critical thinking in the digital environment [2].

The relevance of studying the characteristics of medical terminology in English is associated with the incredibly rapid development of this area. The need for medical translation arises not only at international conferences and councils, but also in the everyday life of specialists in the field of medicine. The features and difficulties that a translator encounters when performing medical translation are of particular importance, since our lives directly depend on the quality of translation.

Teaching English to medical specialists in universities of Uzbekistan requires the implementation of a number of tasks, such as improving study methods, improving the methodology of integration into the specialty and the relationship between subjects. It is important for medical students to master language skills in their field of profession [3].

In connection with the reduction of fundamental subjects in medical universities of Uzbekistan, there is a need to revise the methodology of teaching foreign languages, especially in recent years, since during the modernization of higher medical education there has been a sharp reduction in fundamental subjects, including the subject of foreign languages. Due to significantly reduced teaching hours, there was a need to implement effective and efficient methods of teaching English in a short time. The creation of integrative models of language teaching in the health profession (ESP) is important. Also, creating a special professional environment for language learning has its advantages in teaching English.

There are several key categories, which cover various aspects of medical terminology:

- Medical Personnel: various medical specialties, nurses, and administrative staff of healthcare institutions.
- Diseases and Conditions: the name of various acute and chronic diseases, pathological conditions and symptoms.
- Medical Procedures: surgeries, examinations, tests and various tests.
- Treatment methods: drug therapy, various surgeries, physical therapy, rehabilitation and various other therapeutic interventions.

– **Medical Equipment:** Instruments and equipment used in the diagnosis and treatment of patients, such as stethoscopes, syringes, x-ray machines, etc.

– **Anatomical Terms:** organs, systems and tissues of the body, as well as their functions [4].

Today, the mechanisms for mastering English in a medical school are completely different from what it was before. New forms of learning, introduced as a result of new requirements, the widespread introduction of digital technologies into the educational process, have radically changed the learning of languages, making them accessible and interesting for all social classes and different ages.

The role of digital technologies in the educational process is undeniably high, making a significant contribution to the transformation of traditional teaching methods and providing new opportunities for students and teachers [5].

Digital technologies help enrich learning content by increasing access to a variety of information sources. Virtual labs, interactive learning apps, and online resources create a dynamic and engaging learning environment. This not only promotes a deeper understanding of the course material, but also activates student motivation. Personalization of learning is another important aspect that digital technology brings to education. Adaptive platforms and programs allow teachers to customize the learning process taking into account the individual needs of each student. This promotes more effective learning and accommodates a variety of learning styles. Digital technologies also actively contribute to the development of information literacy among students.

References:

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 11, 2019 No. PP-4391 "On measures to introduce new management principles in the system of higher and secondary specialized education."
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan of October 8, 2019 No. UP-5847 "About approval of the Concept of development of higher education of the Republic of Uzbekistan till 2030".

3. Donovan J. Widening student participation through technology: Universities can gain from employing digital tools in their teaching and learning strategies. *Research Information*. 2017; (93): 15 p.
4. Гурцкой Л.Д. Цифровые компетенции выпускников медицинских вузов России на современном этапе. 2022.
5. Шакирова А.А., Гизятова Л.А. Использование цифровых образовательных ресурсов в процессе преподавания в высшей школе. *Проблемы современного педагогического образования*. 2022; (75/4): 313-316.
6. Попова О.И. Трансформация высшего образования в условиях цифровой экономики. <https://cyberleninka.m/article> [дата обращения: 20.05.2024].
7. Алюнова Т.И. Трансформация образования в условиях цифровизации. *Управление в условиях цифровизации социально-экономических процессов*. 2020; 8-12.
8. Метелькова Л.А., Хрисанова Е.Г., Фролова Е.В. Использование цифровых инструментов в иноязычной подготовке обучающихся. 2024.
9. Даминов Б., Буранова Д. Методы усвоения английского языка в медицинском высшем образовании. *Современные тенденции при обучении иностранному языку в XXI веке*, 1(1), 30–34. <https://inlibrary.uz>. 2023.
10. Буранова Д. The Importance of English Language Learning In the Training of Competitive Staff In Medical Higher Education. *Педиатрия*. №1.264-266. 2021.